

Non Surgical Management of Periapical Lesion of Endodontic Origin: A Conservative Approach

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Abstract

Periapical lesions develop as sequelae to pulp disease. They often occur without any episode of acute pain and are discovered on routine radiographic examination. The incidence of abscesses within periapical lesions varies between 28.7 and 70.07%. The desired result of root canal treatment is based on proper cleaning, disinfecting and shaping of root canals. Calcium Hydroxide is recommended as intracanal medicament because of its antibacterial properties, inhibition of tooth resorption and indication of tissue repair by hard tissue formation. The present case report highlights the use of calcium hydroxide along with iodoform as an inter-appointment endodontic dressing for management of periapical radiolucency. Success rate has been reported upto 85% after endodontic treatment of teeth with periapical lesions. Thus thenon surgicaltreatment of periapical lesions, provided favourable clinical and radiographic response.

Keywords: Periapical Lesion, Non Surgical Endodontic Treatment, Calcium Hydroxide, Healing, iodoform.

Introduction

Periapical lesions of endodontic origin are mostly produced by an inflammatory response at the root apices of teeth with nonvital pulps. It is caused by imbalance between microbial factors and host defenses at the interface between infected radicular pulp and periodontal ligament those results in local inflammation, resorption of hard tissues, destruction of other periapical tissues.¹

A high percentage of 85% of complete and partial healing of periapical lesions following nonsurgical endodontic treatment has been reported. All inflammatory periapical lesions should be initially treated with conservative nonsurgical procedures. Nevertheless the use of intracanal medicament cannot be ignored.²

This case report suggests that surgical removal of periapical lesion of pulpal origin is not mandatory, and that, irrespective of the size and type of the lesion, every effort should be made to treat such lesions by conservative means.³

Case Report

A 21-year old female patient reported to the department of Conservative dentistry and Endodontics at Chandra Dental College and Hospital, Safedabad, Bara banki with a chief complaint fractured teeth in her maxillary anterior region. (#11, #21) Patient gives history of road traffic accident

seven months ago (Fig.1).

Fig 1. Pre-op Clinical photograph

Fig 2. Pre-op Radiograph

The medical history was non contributory and tooth no #11 and #21 was found involved in Ellis Class III Fracture on

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clinical examination. Tooth was sensitive to percussion and pulp vitality test was negative. On the radiographic examination it revealed periapical radiolucency at the apex of maxillary central incisors(Fig.2). Based on history, clinical and radiographic examination, a diagnosis of periapical granuloma was made in relation to #11 and #21.Treatment plan was decided which included non surgical endodontic treatment followed by prosthesis in #11and #21 without surgical intervention. Patient was thoroughly informed about the treatment plan and taken consent form.

First local anesthesia infiltrate(1:80,000 adrenaline with 2% lignocaine) was given, access cavity preparation in #11 and #21 under rubber dam was done with endo-access bur. (Fig.3). Working length determination done with 15 no. kfile, with the help of radiograph(Fig.4) followed by biomechanical preparation using NiTi rotary files system by crown down technique done till 25-6% upto the working length in #11 and #21 respectively.During biomechanical preparation , thorough irrigation done with 3% sodium hypochlorite and 17% EDTA irrigating solutions, along with ultrasonic activation(Fig.5) for the removal of necrosed pulp tissue and debris.

Fig. 3 Access Cavity Preparation under Rubber Dam

Fig. 4 Working Length Radiograph

Fig. 5 Clinical photograph of Irrigation & Ultrasonic activation

After that the root canal was dried with sterile paper points and Intracanal medicament Metapex (Calcium Hydroxide+ Iodoform) was placed into the root canal for 3 months (fig.6), access cavity was restored with glass ionomer cement.

After 3 months, on clinical examination, the teeth #11 and #21 were asymptomatic& intracanal medicament was removed with the help of hand instruments along with copious irrigation of root canal using irrigating solutions. Following the removal of medicament, final irrigation of root canals was done with distilled water and master gutta percha cones were selected.(fig.7)After drying the canals with sterile paper points,root canals were obturated with master gutta percha cones and bioceramic sealer.(SafeEndoBioActive System RCS) (Fig.8)The access cavities were restored with glass ionomer cement followed by prosthesis given in#11 and #21 respectively.(Fig.9,10)Patient was very satisfied with the final treatment outcome.

After 6 months follow up, clinical examination showed no pain and swelling in #11 and in #21and radiographic examination revealed that the periapical radiolucency got significantly minimized. (Fig.11)

Fig. 6 Metapex Dressing Radiograph

Fig. 7 Mastercone Radiograph

Fig. 8 Post-operative Radiograph

Fig. 9 Clinical Photograph with Prosthesis

Fig.10 Post-op Radiograph with Prosthesis

Fig. 11 Follow-up Radiograph after 6-Month

Discussion

Inflammatory periradicular lesions from endodontic origin commonly range between 5 to 8 mm in diameter. Historically, periradicular lesions of up to 10 mm in diameter are considered as periapical granulomas.

Various treatment options presented for large periradicular lesions may range from a root canal therapy to different surgical interventions. Sufficient chemo mechanical cleaning of the root canal system and appropriate disinfection of root canal via intracanal medicament are the most essential factors for achieving satisfactory outcome in non- surgical endodontic treatment.⁴

Previous studies have indicated that nonsurgical RCT should be done at first which according to reports have shown that 42 to 74% of these lesions healed after RCT. In the present case, an antibacterial calcium hydroxide with iodoform based paste was used as intracanal medicament.⁵

Metapex, which contains 60% CH and 38% iodoform in silicone oil as a vehicle is widely used as long term intracanal medicament and its antimicrobial action was evident at deeper tubules in root canals. This premixed, antibacterial paste is used as an intra-canal medicament that has great radiopacity and incredible healing ability.

It is recommended that calcium hydroxide iodoform paste can improve periapical repair and eliminate residual microorganisms via handling the inflammation, stimulation of calcification, nullify acidic products of osteoclasts, and endotoxin neutralization. The antimicrobial effect of calcium hydroxide results from release of hydroxyl ions when it comes in contact with aqueous fluids.⁶

Various biological properties of Calcium hydroxide, such as inhibition of tooth resorption and hard tissue formation. Moreover, it has been shown that calcium hydroxide dressing strongly promotes periapical healing, notably in young adults.

Iodoform is effective as an intracanal medicament, it has also been shown to be host-tissue friendly and hence often used as a resorbable medicament in primary pulpectomies.⁷

The benefits of less invasive nonsurgical treatment of extensive periapical lesion includes minimum psychological trauma and is more acceptable for patients. It seems that the periapical lesion was completely resolved due to rich blood supply, ample undifferentiated cells, and drainage through the lymphatic system.⁸

Conclusion

Periapical granuloma can be effectively controlled without surgery, and recovery can be speeded up by using intracanal medications in conjunction with traditional root canal therapy. In the present case, a periradicular lesion was treated with calcium hydroxide+Iodoform intracanal paste and root canal therapy. This confirms that large inflammatory periapical lesions can heal approvingly by nonsurgical therapy.

A nonsurgical approach should always be adopted before resorting to surgery. The surgical approach can be adopted for cases refractory to nonsurgical treatment, in obstructed or non-negotiable canals and for cases where long-term monitoring of periapical lesions is not possible.

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